

THE FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF JOINTS IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS: A LITERATURE REVIEW AND EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Marino Quaresimin

*Department of Management and Engineering - University of Padova
Stradella S.Nicola 3 - 36100 VICENZA - ITALY
E-mail: marino.quaresimin@unipd.it*

SUMMARY: The paper presents the first results of a research program aiming to the definition of methodologies and procedures for the fatigue design of composite-composite joints. After a brief discussion about the literature on composite connections and available models and data, the experimental results on the static and fatigue behavior of co-cured stepped lap joints are presented and discussed. The results of a careful damage evolution analysis identify in the delamination at the layer's interface the mechanism controlling the failure of the joints and they allow to justify the average increase in the joint strength, both in static and fatigue tests, as the layer overlap increases. The presence of the connection induces however a significant reduction, up the 45%, in the laminate static strength and a strong sensitivity to the fatigue damage, with a joint fatigue strength at 2 million cycles ranging from of 30% to 48% of its static strength.

KEYWORDS: carbon-epoxy woven fabric composite, stepped lap joints, fatigue strength, damage analysis.

INTRODUCTION

A typical problem the designers have to face during the development of a new product in composite material (or in repairing an existing structure) is the presence of joints, metal inserts and openings for the connection of the composite parts between them and to the remaining part of the structure [1-2]. A quite common solution in the practical applications is to bond together the different parts to be joined. Joints can be needed also for manufacturing reasons related to the geometry of the component, when some overlapping has to be done, for instance during the plies lay-up, thus creating what is called a stepped lap joint.

The development of suitable and reliable design tools for the prediction of strength and life of composite connections has been considered for a long time by the scientific community, see refs. [3-12] for some examples. In spite of this, the available models often turn out difficult to be generalized and their application to industrial components is very far from easy even for the strong influence that different design parameters can have on the joint fatigue behavior, as illustrated in the extensive and worthwhile bibliographic analysis presented in [13]. It is therefore convenient to focus the attention on the development of suitable design methodologies, because, for composite materials components, all the benefits provided by their application, such as lightness and high specific strength, may be deeply harmed by an improper or over-designed joining or by the use of too high safety coefficients.

With the aim to provide a contribution in this area, a joined research project has been sponsored by the Italian Ministry of Research and University. The main objective of the research program is the definition of methodologies and procedures for the fatigue design of composite-composite joints suitable for transferring to the fatigue design of real components the information and the strength data obtained from the characterization in laboratory, usually done on specimens and joints of reduced dimensions. The experimental investigation of the project is mainly oriented to analyze the static and fatigue behavior of several configurations of composite-composite bonded and stepped lap joints. In this paper the first experimental results on stepped lap joints are presented and discussed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A re-analysis of the technical literature, with reference to the bonded and molded joints in composite materials, highlighted the presence of a quite large number of experimental data due to the great attention paid to the problem by many researchers in the last 25 years. Many investigations relate to crack propagation problems and only a reduced number of research projects, see as an example [5, 7, 9, 14-24], were oriented to evaluate the load carrying capability of the joints as structural load-bearing parts of a structure. This is justified by the analysis of the fatigue damage evolution in composite joints which indicates in the crack initiation and in the subsequent crack growth, up to the final failure of the joint, the main damage mechanisms.

Nevertheless, the available data are not enough and, further, not suitable for the definition of reliable fatigue design rules and methodologies, neither for the validation of the available prediction models mainly because they refer to design conditions too much different in terms of geometry, parent material and adhesives. The systematic re-analysis of the data collected from literature suggested therefore the most critical parameters for the subsequent experimental activity of the project.

Several different approaches have been applied to the life prediction of composite bonded joints:

Ishii and co-Authors [5] suggested that the high cycle fatigue strength of CFRP/metal adhesive joints under multiaxial stress conditions can be estimated by the maximum principal stress in the adhesive layer. Again in the case of multiaxial loading, Nayeb-Hashemi and co-Authors [4] proposed a model to predict the fatigue life on the basis of a damage parameter which accounts for the combined effects of the stress fields due to the external multiaxial loads.

In another work, Ishii and co-Authors [7], in order to consider the stress singularity at the corners of the adhesive/adherent interface, based the fatigue life estimation on two "apparent" values for stress intensity factor and degree of singularity of the stress field in the critical zone of the joint.

It is the opinion of the author that a more promising and precise way to describe and model the fatigue life is that which accounts for the actual evolution of the damage: a initiation or nucleation phase followed by a crack growth. It has been found that the fraction of the life spent in the two phases depends on many parameters like joint geometry, stress distributions, stress ratio, adhesive type and thickness, environmental conditions and others. In adhesive joints a crack usually nucleates and grows mainly in the adhesive or at the adhesive/adherent interface and therefore the life to crack initiation can be estimated using a generalized stress intensity factor approach, as already proposed and described in refs. [6, 10]. The duration of the following propagation phase can be later assessed by integrating a suitable power law relating the crack growth rate to the maximum strain energy release rate (SERR). [3, 8, 12].

As it will be discussed later, in the stepped cured joints the damage evolves in a more complex way, starting with a transversal crack in the matrix where the layers are joined, followed by the onset and growth of delaminations at the layer's interfaces. In this case a slightly different approach should be adopted, with a procedure similar to that proposed in [9]. The onset of the transversal cracks can be assessed by generating a fatigue life curve in terms of the local stress or strain fields, while for the onset of the delamination a relationship between the total SERR and the number of cycles to delamination onset have to be established. The final propagation phase can be evaluated again by integration of a crack growth rate/SERR power law.

MATERIALS AND SPECIMEN PREPARATION

The stepped lap joints were obtained from laminate panels manufactured starting from a SEAL - TEXIPREG® CC206 - ET442 prepreg (twill 2x2 T300 carbon fibre fabric, CIBA 5021 toughened epoxy matrix, $V_f = 60\%$). The panels were produced in two lay-ups, namely $[0]_8$ and $[0_2/45_2]_8$, by vacuum bag autoclave molding with a curing cycle at 120° C and pressure of 0.6 MPa for 60 minutes. The joints were cut from the panels using a diamond saw and provided with end-tabs to prevent damage induced by the machine grips. The joint dimensions are shown in Fig.1 where it is also reported the configuration chosen for simulating the connection. The different layers are laid-up in

sequence by keeping constant the overlap length along the whole thickness; series of joints with overlap length 3, 5 and 8 mm, respectively, were analyzed.

The edges of some joints were polished for the microscopic investigations used to analyze the damage evolution during the fatigue life and identify the typical damage mechanisms and patterns.

Fig.1 Joint geometry

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS AND RESULTS

The static behavior of the joints was investigated by means of tensile tests under displacement control with a crosshead speed equal to 2 mm/min. The fatigue tests were carried out in tension-tension ($R=0.05$), under load control with a sinusoidal wave and a test frequency variable in the range from 5 to 15 Hz depending on lay-up and stress level, up to the complete separation of the specimen.

All the specimens were tested at room temperature on a servo-hydraulic MTS 809 machine with a 10/100 kN load cell. The evolution of the fatigue damage was carefully analyzed by applying several experimental techniques, such as strain gauges, infrared thermography, x-radiography, optical and SEM microscopy. In order to do this, some specimens were subjected to constant amplitude blocks of loading up to failure. At the end of each block the test was suspended and the specimen was analyzed.

The tensile static properties of the parent laminates, without connection, are listed in table 1, while table 2 summarizes the tensile static properties of the joints in the different configurations. For each condition five repeated tests were carried out. The strain level in the joints was calculated simply by dividing the joint elongation by the joint length outside the end tabs.

In Figure 2 the average strength properties are plotted versus the overlap length after being normalized with respect to the parent laminate strength. Two considerations can be made:

- there is a significant reduction in the laminate strength, up to 45 % in the worst cases, due to the presence of the connection, independently of the lay-up;
- for both the lay-up, the increase of the overlap length from 3 to 5 mm increases the joint strength of about 15%, while a longer overlap of 8 mm brings no further strength benefits. This means that, from the static point of view, the saturation of load carrying capability of the joints can be reached with a ply overlap length of about 5 mm.

In terms of stress-strain relationship, the $[0]_8$ joints exhibit a linear elastic behavior up to failure, with a final sudden failure due to the unstable growth of a transversal crack, while during the test of $[0_2/45_2]_s$ joints the layers oriented at 45° fail first, with a drop in the load carrying capability of the joint. This is shown by the discontinuity in the tensile curves plotted in Fig. 3, which typifies the behavior of the joints with quasi-isotropic lay-up.

Table 1 – Tensile strength and elastic properties of the laminates

Lay-up	σ_{uts} [MPa]	c.o.v [%]	ϵ_{uts} [%]	c.o.v [%]	E [MPa]	c.o.v
$[0]_8$	643,68	9,31	1,49	15,25	55076	2,28
$[0_2/45_2]_s$	436,78	3,87	1,41	3,29	38765	1,31

Table 2 – Tensile strength properties of the joints (average of five tests for each condition)

Lay-up	Code	Overlap [mm]	σ_{UTS} [MPa]	c.o.v. [%]	ϵ_{UTS} [%]	c.o.v. [%]	$\frac{\sigma_{UTS-joint}}{\sigma_{UTS-laminate}}$
[0] ₈	S03	3	359,9	2,50	0,80	4,68	55.9
	S05	5	420,4	5,51	0,90	3,96	65.3
	S08	8	425,0	2,55	0,91	2,34	66.0
[0 ₂ /45 ₂] _s	SQI3	3	245,1	3,47	0,80	4,02	56.1
	SQI5	5	283,1	1,15	1	3,86	64.8
	SQI8	8	271,0	4,57	1,03	3,93	62.0

Fig.2: Comparison of the normalized joint strength

Fig.3: Typical tensile curve for a [0₂/45₂]_s joint

The fatigue data were statistically analyzed under the hypothesis of log-normal distribution of cycles to failure. The results of the analysis are summarized in Table 3 where the average reference stress at $2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles ($\sigma_{MAX,50\%PS}$) as well as that referred to a probability of survival of 90% ($\sigma_{MAX,90\%PS}$) are reported. The same values are then normalized with respect to the relevant static strength of the joint, thus obtaining the fatigue ratios $\phi_{50\%}$ e $\phi_{90\%}$, reported in the table together with the values of slope k of Wöhler curves and scatter index T_σ ($T_\sigma = \sigma_{MAX,10\%PS} / \sigma_{MAX,90\%PS}$). Normalized fatigue data and average fatigue curves are plotted in Figs. 4 and 5.

The results of the tests carried out till now indicate clearly a significant influence of the ply overlap length on the fatigue strength of the joints and this is more evident for the [0]₁₀ lay-up. This difference with respect to the static behavior can be explained, as discussed later, on the basis of the damage evolution which involves, in the last phase of the fatigue life, a growth of the delamination at the layers interface. It cannot be excluded therefore that further increases in the overlap length could bring to improvements in the joint fatigue strength.

Table 3 – Results of the statistical analysis on the fatigue data of the different series (fatigue strength values at $2 \cdot 10^6$ cycles)

series	No. of data	$\sigma_{MAX,50\%PS}$ [MPa]	ϕ_{50} [%]	$\sigma_{MAX,90\%PS}$ [MPa]	ϕ_{90} [%]	k	T_σ
S03	8 (1 r.o.)	108,96	30,27	93,66	26,02	10,89	1,353
S05	8 (1 r.o.)	138,82	33,02	121,08	28,80	8,57	1,314
S08	8 (1 r.o.)	203,15	47,80	191,25	45	9,39	1.129
SQI3	7 (1 r.o.)	75,95	30,99	70,43	28,74	9,73	1,163
SQI5	8 (1 r.o.)	102,07	36,05	87,03	30,74	10,55	1,375
SQI8	7 (2 r.o.)	104,78	38,66	99,23	36,61	8,17	1,115

Fig.4: Fatigue data for $[0]_{10}$ joints

Fig.5: Fatigue data for $[0_2/45_2]_s$ joints

FATIGUE DAMAGE EVOLUTION

Typical damage patterns observed from specimens at different fraction of fatigue life tests are shown in Figs. 6 and 7. Some micrographs representative of the different experimental evidences are also reported in Figs 8-11. The microscopic observations were carried out on joints fatigued at a maximum stress level of 50%-60% of the relevant static strength.

For all the joint configurations, damage initiates at low fractional life (5-10%) as the growth of transversal cracks in the zones where two plies are joined, as depicted in Figs. 6a, 7a and 8. The further evolution was instead different depending on the joint lay-up. For $[0]_8$ joints, the onset of delamination in the joints with 3 and 5 mm ply overlap was observed after more than half of the fatigue life (Figs. 6b and 9). For the longer overlap, instead, the transversal cracks was noticed at 5% of life and the onset of delamination at about 10% of life. It is interesting to note the evolution in length and width of the transversal cracks as the life spent increases, shown in Fig.10.

For $[0_2/45_2]_s$ joints, the onset of delamination at the interface of the external 0° layers was observed quite earlier after the nucleation of the transversal cracks. The delamination grows along the interface of the external layers and then pass to the inner 45° layers (Figs. 7b and 11). At that point, the load carrying capability of the joint is compromised, resulting in a sudden failure.

On the basis of the available results it is still difficult to definitely identify a trend, so further tests at approximately the same life and observations are in progress in order to clarify this point. Nevertheless, the fatigue damage evolution can be separated in three main phases: crack initiation, delamination onset and propagation up the final failure of joint. It is worth noting that a longer overlap means a longer time spent in the delamination growth phase allowing to justify the influence of the ply overlap length on the fatigue strength. As already discussed previously, the phases of the damage evolution have to be properly modeled in the attempt to define a reliable life prediction method for this type of structural connection.

Fig. 6 Typical damage patterns of $[0]_{10}$ joints after (a) 5-10% and (b) 70-80% of the fatigue life

Fig.7 Typical damage patterns of $[0_2/45_2]_S$ joints after (a) 5-10% and (b) 70-80% of the fatigue life

Fig. 8: Transversal crack in the first layer of a $[0]_{10}$ joint (overlap 3mm) loaded at 50% of σ_{UTS} after 10% of its fatigue life

Fig. 9: Transversal cracks and delaminations in the first and second layer of a $[0]_{10}$ joint (overlap 3mm) loaded at 50% of σ_{UTS} after 60% of its fatigue life

Fig. 10: Transversal crack growth in the second layer of a $[0]_{10}$ joint (overlap 5mm) loaded at 50% of σ_{UTS} after 15, 50 and 75% of its fatigue life (micrographs taken at the same joint position)

Fig. 11: Transversal cracks and delaminations in the first, second and third layer of a $[0_2/45_2]_S$ joint (overlap 3mm) loaded at 50% of σ_{UTS} after 85% of its fatigue life

COMPARISON WITH LITERATURE DATA ON STEPPED LAP JOINTS

The behavior of this class of joints is not well documented in literature and only one journal paper was found on this subject till now [18]. The investigation was oriented to analyze the static and fatigue tensile strength of unidirectional carbon/epoxy joints with overlap length of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mm respectively, and two joint configurations: simultaneously cured joint and joint manufactured in two phases.

For the simultaneously cured joints, the static strength was found to increase continuously with the ply overlap length, as one could have expected by considering the short overlap between the plies. This is in good agreement with our results plotted in Fig.2; we also found, in fact, an increase in strength for ply overlap up to 5 mm.

The fatigue results, related to tension-tension tests carried out at a stress ratio $R=0.1$, show an increase in fatigue strength with the increase of the ply overlap. Moreover the Authors were able to summarize the normalized fatigue data in a common fatigue scatter band. This is quite in contrast with our results presented in Figs. 4 and 5 and summarized in table 3. An attempt of synthesis could be done only for the series with shorter overlap (3 and 5 mm), even considering the actual scatter of the data. Unfortunately no details about the fatigue damage evolution are reported in ref. [18] for further clarification of this difference.

CONCLUSIONS

The behavior of stepped lap cocured joints in carbon epoxy woven composite was analyzed and discussed. The presence of this type of connection in a laminate panel affect significantly its strength properties.

The ply overlap length turned out to have a greater influence on the fatigue strength than on the static properties, with an increase in the fatigue strength as the overlap increases. This behavior can be justified on the basis of the damage evolution during the fatigue life of the joint

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was carried out in the frame of the project "*Fatigue design methodologies of joints in composite material*" (2001092449) financially supported by the Italian Ministry of Research and University.

REFERENCES

1. Davis M., Bond D., Principles and practice of adhesive bonded structural joints and repairs, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 1999, vol.19, pp.91-105
2. Quaresimin M., Meneghetti G. and Verardo F., Design and optimisation of a RTM composite bicycle crank, *Journal of Reinforced Plastic and Composites* 2001, vol. 20, pp.129-146.
3. Kinloch A.J. , Osiyemi S.O., Predicting the Fatigue Life of Adhesively-Bonded Joints, *Journal of Adhesion*, 1993, vol. 43, pp.79-90.
4. Nayeb-Hashemi H., Rossettos J.N., Melo A.P., Multiaxial fatigue life evaluation of tubular adhesively bonded joints, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 1997, vol.17, pp.55-63.
5. Ishii K., Imanaka M., Nakayama H., Kodama H., Fatigue failure criterion of adhesively bonded CFRP/metal joints under multiaxial stress conditions, *Composites Part A*, 1998, vol. 29A, pp. 415-422.
6. Lefebvre D.R. e Dillard D.A., A stress singularity approach for the prediction of fatigue crack initiation in adhesive bonds. Part I: theory", *Journal of Adhesion*, 1999, vol. 70, pp. 119-138.
7. Ishii K., Imanaka M., Nakayama H., Kodama H., Evaluation of the fatigue strength of adhesively bonded CFRP/metal single and single-step double-lap joints, *Composite Science and Technology* 1999, vol.59 pp. 1675-1683.
8. Curley A. J., Hadavinia H., Kinloch A. J., Taylor A. C., Predicting the service-life of adhesively-bonded joints, *International Journal of Fracture*, 2000, vol.103, pp.41-69.
9. Krueger R., Paris I.L, O'Brien T.K., Fatigue Life Methodology for Bonded Composite Skin/Stringer Configurations, In Proc. of the 15th ASC Technical Conference (2000) pp. 729-736, Technomic Publishing, ISBN 1-58716-053-6.
10. Lazzarin P., Quaresimin M., Ferro P., A two-term stress function approach to evaluate stress distributions in bonded joints of different geometries, *Journal of Strain Analysis*, 2002, vol. 37, pp.385-398
11. Mortensen F., Thomsen O.T., Analysis of adhesive bonded joints: a unified approach, *Composites Science and Technology*, 2002, vol. 62, pp.1011 –1031.
12. Abdel Wahab M.M., Ashcroft I.A., Crocombe A.D., Smith P.A., Numerical prediction of fatigue crack propagation lifetime in adhesively bonded structures, *International Journal of Fatigue*, 2002, vol.24, pp.705-709.
13. De Goeij W.C., van Tooren M.J.L., Beukers A., Composite adhesive joints under cyclic loading, *Materials and design*, 1999, vol.20, pp.213-221.
14. Renton W.J., Vinson J.R. Fatigue behavior of bonded joints in composite material structures, *Journal of Aircraft*, 1974, vol. 12, pp. 442-447.
15. Krause A. R., Holubka J. W., Chun W., The effect of adhesive chemistry on the fatigue resistance of adhesive bonds in service environment, *Advanced Composites: The Latest Developments*, Proc. of the 2nd Conference (1986), pp. 193-201.
16. Okuda S., Nishina S., Watanabe T., On Fatigue behaviours of bonded joints of FRP, Proc. of the 30th Japan Congress on Material Research (1987), pp. 253-256.
17. Reedy Jr. E. D., Guess T.R., Composite-to-metal tubular lap joints: strength and fatigue resistance, *International Journal of Fracture*, 1993, vol.63, pp. 351-367.

18. Kim H.S., Lee S.J., Lee D. G., Development of a strength model for the cocured stepped lap joints under tensile loading, *Composite Structures*, 1995, vol.32, pp.593-600
19. Knox E.M., Bowling M.J., Haschim S.A., Fatigue performance of adhesively bonded connections in GRE pipes, *International journal of fatigue*, 2000, vol.20, 513-519.
20. Briskham P., Smith G., Cyclic stress durability testing of lap shear joints exposed to hot-wet conditions, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2000, vol. 20, pp. 33-38.
21. Ashcroft I.A., Abdel Wahab M.M., Crocombe A.D., Hughes D.J., Shaw S.J., The effect of environment on the fatigue of bonded composite joints. Part 1: testing and fractography, *Composites: Part A*, 2001, vol. 32, pp.59-69.
22. Potter K.D., Guild F.J., Harvey H.J., Wisnom M.R., Adams R.D., Understanding and control of adhesive crack propagation in bonded joints between carbon fibre composite adherends I. Experimental, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 2001, vol. 21, pp.435-443.
23. Aymerich F., Priolo P., Fatigue behaviour of cocured stitched joints in composite material, Proc. of XXXI AIAS National conference, September 2002, Parma - Italy, (in Italian).
24. Ferreira J.A.M., Reis P.N., Costa J.D.M., Richardson M.O.W., Fatigue behaviour of composite adhesive lap joints”, *Composites Science and Technology*, 2002, vol. 62, pp. 1373-1379.